

Somaliland and Ethiopia New Diplomatic Relations:
Dr. Abiy's foreign policy towards Somaliland

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Abstract

This article will critically examine the ramifications of Ethiopia's political transformation under Dr. Abiy on Somaliland-Ethiopian relations, notably Somaliland's qua status. It investigates which of the Ethiopian authoritarian regimes run by the TPLF or Abiy's democratic government is better for the survival and recognition of Somaliland. First, it will scrutinize whether Ethiopia, led by the TPLF, has ever wanted to recognize Somaliland as an independent state. It will be accomplished by contrasting Abiy's Ethiopia with the TPLF's Ethiopia. Second, it will illustrate which of Abiy's or the TPLF's terms for Somaliland is more likely to be recognized as a sovereign state. The study argues that Ethiopia's new democratic government, led by Dr. Abiy, may not recognize Somaliland as an independent state from Somalia, as did Ethiopia's previous government, led by the TPLF, but the difference is that Dr. Abiy is a leader for Horn of African decolonization, whereas the TPLF's was a colonial agent who planned to erase the Somali nation, including Somalia and Somaliland, from the world map.

Introduction

The Horn of Africa region, unlike the rest of Africa, has been in turmoil since colonial times. However, the politics of Ethiopia, the region's most powerful country, shifted in 2018. It was a significant step forward in the region's democratization and freedom from Western colonization. Dr. Abiy, Ethiopia's democratically elected Prime Minister, led the transformation, which has had a significant impact on the area, particularly in Somalia and Eritrea, and the Horn of Africa region in general. Following the ratification of a tripartite agreement on regional integration between Somalia, Ethiopia, and Eritrea, Somaliland perceived the development as a threat to its own survival. Somaliland considered the agreements, particularly those between Somalia and Ethiopia, a threat to its very existence because they (agreements) indicated that both Ethiopia and Somalia, the country from which Somaliland sought independence, would preserve the sovereignty of both Somalia and Ethiopia. This has a direct impact on Somaliland's sovereignty, which is attempting to win international recognition for its independence from Somalia. As a result, Dr. Abiy looked to regard Somaliland as an extension of Somalia, and because of that, Somaliland regarded Dr. Abiy as a foe.

This was heightened after the deposed TPLF claimed that it would pursue recognition for Somaliland during its term in power in Ethiopia, but Dr. Abiy is an ignorant guy who wants to put Somaliland under Somalia's rule. They made this declaration before the TPLF declared war on Dr. Abiy's government. This statement was intended to arouse Somaliland's desire to join an alliance with the TPLF to depose Dr. Abiy. Somaliland, on the other hand, has adopted a neutral approach rather than designating Dr. Abiy an enemy, despite the fact that they saw him as one.

Shortly as the situation deteriorated, the TPLF published another statement criticizing Dr. Abiy, calling him a lunatic. "Abiy is a crazy man because he wants our enemies, Somaliland and Somalia, to unite and destroy us," Getajo told the BBC. Unfortunately, many in Somaliland have not paid attention to this latest announcement, but they have paid heed to the TPLF's previous statement, in which it stated its desire to recognize Somaliland.

As a result, since the Somaliland separatists believe Tplf's lies and are unable to perceive Tplf's enmity toward Somalis, this article attempts to shine light on Tplf's genuine emotions toward

Somaliland and all Somalis. It also focuses on Dr. Abiy's view on Somaliland, comparing the Tplf's perspective on Somaliland to his government's perspective to determine whether there are any disparities regarding Somaliland's recognition. It'll also explain why Dr. Abiy first minimized Somaliland's diplomatic ties with his country and then improved them. It will also examine if Dr. Abiy can be persuaded to recognize Somaliland.

The contrast in foreign policies between Dr. Abiy and the TPLF regarding Somaliland's bid for recognition

During the TPLF's rule, Ethiopia saw three factors as a deterrent. First, Ethiopia's led TPLF viewed the reunification of Somaliland and Somalia as a deterrent to its federated nation state and geopolitical ambitions in the Horn of Africa. The second thing it did not want was for Somaliland to become an independent state, which it believed would jeopardize its own interests in Somaliland. The third factor was that it did not want South Somalia to have a functioning government.

For three reasons, Ethiopia has never enthusiastically consented to recognizing Somaliland. The first reason is that Ethiopia has a hostile perception towards the Somali ethnic group in the different territories, which has historically been a foe. It is also worth noting that, despite the fact that Somaliland seceded from Somalia and signed a peace treaty with Ethiopia, this was insufficient. They believed the idea that "Somalia is typically Somali wherever it is." This means Somalis are enemies, whether they are from Somaliland or Somalia.

The second reason was that recognizing Somaliland would provide Somaliland with sovereignty. Because of this sovereignty, the two countries, Ethiopia and Somaliland, had to be subject to the same status quo. According to Ethiopia, this results in two unpleasant outcomes for Ethiopia. First, promoting Ethiopia's interests in Somaliland, a comparatively small, weaker, and unrecognized country, would be more expensive or have a higher cost because Somaliland is not supposed to rely on Ethiopia any more for regaining recognition since it is already recognized and has sovereignty. The third reason is that, because Somaliland is set to become an independent Somali state, the number of nations or states and power of Somalis in the region would grow. This is

because Somaliland, which used to be part of Somalia before 1991 before being split off, is in the most important place in the world and is still hostile to Ethiopia.

Ethiopia was not pleased with the possible formation of a new independent, democratic, and stable Somali state (Somaliland) in the region. This is owing to the contrasts between the two governing systems. Ethiopia is a multi-ethnic nation-state, whereas Somalis constitute a single ethnic group in both Somalia and Somaliland. In short, Ethiopia is a nation state, Somalis are a nation, and Somaliland is a nation if it stands alone. So, if Ethiopia becomes a country that is surrounded by Muslim Somali states like Somalia, Somaliland, and Djibouti, which could become powerful at any time in the future, this could help Somali countries work together to fight Ethiopia.

Instead, Ethiopia has abandoned its plan to colonize all Somalis in Somalia and Somaliland. This was not an easy job, but it set the stage for the plan to keep Somaliland's status as unrecognized and Somalia in turmoil. Once they have done so, the world is finally convinced that Somalis are unable to govern themselves, and Ethiopia is the closest country that can. At the very least, Somaliland and Somalia should be given up to Ethiopia and Kenya, respectively.

Ethiopia's most complicated mission was to prevent the unification of Somaliland and Somalia because it saw it as a threat in two ways: first, because Ethiopia has Somali territory, which is the Somali region of Ethiopia and is suppressed; thus, it feared that if Somalis united and gained power, they would claim the region, as happened when the two countries went to war in 1977. The second challenge was that, during Somalia's absence from the world political arena, Ethiopia became the most powerful country in the Horn of Africa. This looked like it was going away, and Somalia would have to fight Ethiopia for power in the Horn of Africa, which meant Ethiopia had lost power in the region.

For all of these reasons, Ethiopia decided to devise a strategy to keep Somalis out of politics, and in order to gain support for this strategy, Ethiopia began cooperating with Western colonialists. Eventually, Ethiopia succeeded in demonstrating to Western countries, who are highly interested in their continuing colonialism of the Horn of Africa, that they can be loyal representatives in the Horn of Africa for Western colonialism and do whatever they want for them. They cite three reasons why Tigreans might be a more devoted representative of the West and fare better in terms

of Western ties than Somalis: To begin with, the Tigreans are Christian, which makes them more devoted to Westerners than Muslim Somalis. Second, because they are a small ethnic minority in Ethiopia and reside in an area where ethnic tensions are rampant, they may be loyal to the Westerners. Third, they have government expertise because they have been a kingdom for thousands of years. As a result, Ethiopians and Westerners can collaborate to eliminate Somalis from the region.

As long as these things were true, the West agreed with Ethiopia to implement its plan to eradicate any Somali nation in order to take over their land and strategic location in Africa, steal their resources, and change their culture, language, and religion so that the Somali people wouldn't know who they were. They also thought that Somalis were hard to get to give up to Western colonialism because they are Muslims of the same ethnicity who believe in supremacy and live in a very important geographical location.

Ethiopia not only kept the region's countries unstable, but it also exemplified the West very well. This is clear in how the West threatened Ethiopia's democratic government, which was brought about by a suppressed mass movement led by Dr. Abiy Ahmed in 2018. Ethiopia's TPLF regime was ousted by the people of Ethiopia and a democratically elected government took its place. Abiy's government has brought about significant changes in the country and in neighboring countries, and although he took steps that it cannot be summarized here, his memorable accomplishments include releasing political prisoners, closing down prisons like Ogaden, which were used to brutally torture Somali innocents, freeing people and the press, and allowing women to participate in politics and become cabinet members. In terms of foreign policy, the TPLF's antagonism towards Ethiopia's neighbors, like Eritrea and Somalia, was ended.

As a result, ties between the Tigray region, led by the TPLF, and the federal government deteriorated. This occurred when the TPLF, believing it had lost influence over the government, declared that they would not recognize Dr. Abiy while he remained a loyal leader of his country and region in the Horn of Africa and opposed the Westerners when he refused to do the work that the TPLF used as an agent for the West. As a result, the TPLF and the West collaborated to depose the Abiy government and restore colonial rule to the region. The TPLF launched an attack on the government in order to destabilize it. The West's response has been to back the TPF, a rebel group

that mishandled the country and region throughout its rule. The western countries, including the USA, on the other hand, resisted Dr. Abiy and levied sanctions on his government until the democratic government was forced to refrain from prosecuting the criminal TPLF members.

However, the issue I want to highlight is this. The huge political progress made by Dr. Abiy's leadership in the promotion of regional integration in the HOA has helped Somaliland invisibly. From Somalia's near-independence in 1960 until 2018, the first time the two countries crossed the border peacefully and with respect was when Dr. Abiy took over as Ethiopia's leader. However, the people of Somaliland, who are strongly willing to secede from Somalia, and the Somaliland government, on the other hand, saw Dr. Abiy as a threat to Somaliland's existence as he had a strong relationship with the president of the federal government of Somalia, H.E. Mohamed Abilahi Farmajo. Because of that, they thought that Dr. Abiy wanted to make Somalia and Somaliland one, so he didn't respect Somaliland's independence.

Abiy was incorrect in the eyes of the Somaliland people. However, two things should be noted. First, he was a leader of unity and fraternity in the Horn of Africa, as he was committed to unifying the region, much like the European Union. Second, he was not a Somalilander brother who could appreciate Somaliland's unique interests. He, like some Somalilanders, believed that unity was preferable to separation, and he did not consider Somaliland to be an independent state under international law. It is also vital to note that no international or African leader is permitted to recognize Somaliland's independence since, even if he is pleased with Somaliland's independence, international law forbids it. However, he believed that the benefits of unity outweighed the benefits of separation.

However, Ethiopia's political transition and Prime Minister Dr. Abiy's reign benefited Somaliland. It is necessary and valuable for the region, like the people of the Horn of Africa, to re-liberate itself from colonial authority in Somaliland in order to achieve a better existence. Apart from Somaliland's specific interests, support for Dr. Abiy's ambition to succeed in the Horn of Africa would put an end to dictatorship in the region, interstate and intrastate conflict, and restore the honor and integrity of the Somali identity. It would also end Africa's scourges of poverty, recurrent drought, suppression, oppression, human rights violations, brain drain, and civil conflict. In terms

of Somaliland's recognition, if it had been liberated from the West, Somaliland might not have lost its rights.

Finally, it appears that Dr. Abiy Ahmed examined Somaliland matters in early 2022, following the appointment of Ethiopia's ambassador to Somaliland to strengthen diplomatic ties with Somaliland. This could mean one of two things: when the West put so much pressure on him to halt great momentum in the Horn of Africa, Dr. Abiy was forced to forsake his efforts at regional reintegration and treat Somaliland as it has always been. Or it's possible that he's realized that Somaliland has a high level of diplomacy in the globe that he was previously unaware of.

In terms of statehood, Somaliland, on the other hand, deserves to be considered as an independent country. In comparison to the country from which it wishes to secede, Somaliland is an existing and functioning democracy, whereas Somalia, for whatever reason, is a failed state that has been without an effective government for nearly 30 years and cannot pass the capital, Mogadishu, despite the fact that order has been restored in recent years when Farmajo came to power. Somaliland is a peaceful and stable country, whereas Somalia is a violent yet recognized country, but Somaliland is not. Aside from the fact that Somaliland is not recognized, all of these considerations may contribute to Dr. Abiy respecting Somaliland.

Nevertheless, Dr. Abiy's advancement of his country's diplomatic relations with Somaliland has had no effect on the relationship between Somalia and Ethiopia for two reasons. To begin with, everybody can see that Dr. Abiy is unable to recognize Somaliland as an independent state since the situation between Ethiopia and Somalia, the country from which Somaliland wishes to separate, would not enable him to do so. In other words, Ethiopia is a federal nation state that rules a Somali ethnic region state (Somali regional federal state of Ethiopia) that has always wanted the opportunity to secede from Ethiopia. Ethiopia, a country on the verge of disintegration, is home to a diverse range of ethnic groups. It is a country that, like Yugoslavia, can be divided into separate states at any time. As a result, he will not recognize a country (Somaliland) that wishes to break away from Somalia. The second reason Dr. Abiy can't recognize Somaliland is because he is a unionist leader who wants to keep the Horn of Africa as a whole.

Conclusion

To summarize, both Ethiopia's Democratic Government, led by Dr. Abiy, and the defunct totalitarian TPLF dictatorship opposed recognizing Somaliland as an independent state, albeit for different reasons. However, it is a false assumption that the TPLF-ruled Ethiopia had friendly relations with Somaliland and wanted Somaliland to be recognized as an independent state, but was hostile only to Somalia, with the goal of shedding light on Dr. Abiy and demonstrating that he is opposed to Somaliland and its quest for recognition. It is true that the TPLF has never been faithful to the existence and recognition of Somaliland because the TPLF has been a colonial agent and antagonistic to Somali ethnicity, and has seen this as a threat to its own national interest in Somaliland, which it has always used to obtain cheaply and easily. Dr. Abiy, on the other hand, had no issues with Somaliland or Somalia. He considered regional unity to be more vital than anything else, hence he prioritized the unification of Somalia and Somaliland.

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